

PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES

LITANY OF LORETO (LITANIA LAURETANA) - THE FIRST GEORGIAN PRINTED PRAYER

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Abstract

Among humanity's intellectual achievements, the printing press, which was created in the 17th century, holds a special place. Even in the conditions of the global character of contemporary scientific-technical progress, the printed word remains the most flexible and comprehensive means of information. This is the characteristic that it has possessed at all stages of its development. Throughout the centuries, the printed word appears in the role of informer and educator, as well as an invaluable means of exchanging cultural values among peoples. This is also confirmed by the history of Georgian printed books.

The first Georgian printed publications are: "Georgian Alphabet with Prayers," "Georgian-Italian Dictionary," the Georgian translation of the Catholic prayer "Litania Lauretana," and Francesco-Maria Maggio's "Georgian Grammar." Despite the fact that "Litania Lauretana" is a Catholic prayer, it enjoyed no less popularity and respect among the Christian population of the entire Orthodox East. A review of the Georgian translation of "Litania Lauretana" allows for the unmistakable general conclusion that already in the 17th century, the printed word represented a quite effective weapon for achieving both political and religious purposes.

Keywords: printed publications, "Propaganda Fide," missionary activities, Catholic prayer.

Introduction: The establishment of the Georgian printed word and the initial stage of its development coincided with such a difficult historical period in our people's life when the possibility of implementing cultural measures in Georgia was almost excluded. Four centuries have passed since the first Georgian book was printed. This event was significant in the life of the Georgian people, who faced severe conditions of historical development. They had to take up the sword before they could take up the pen. It was precisely this circumstance that determined that the first Georgian printed books were printed outside Georgia's borders, in Italy, thereby laying the foundation for the centuries-old printing tradition of Georgian literature.

Among the measures implemented by the Roman Church at the beginning of the 17th century, one of the most significant was bringing missionary activities to the forefront. Papal authority used every means to acquire new congregants in Eastern countries through the spread of the Catholic faith. The idea of forming a central organ for Catholic missionary work was conceived as early as the 14th century, though only in 1622, during the time of Pope Gregory XV, was the society for propagating the Catholic faith, *Sacra Congregatio de Propaganda Fide*, created. In 1988, Pope John Paul II reorganized the Congregation, as a result of which it was transformed into the Congregation for the Evangelization of Peoples - *Congregatio pro Gentium Evangelizatione*. The organization's leaders tasked missionaries with studying the language of the country where they would have to work. For this purpose, appropriate literature was necessary - grammar books, dictionaries, the Bible, and other liturgical books. Naturally, "Propaganda Fide" faced the issue of providing this institution with its own printing press. In 1626, the decision was made to create a printing press, and its technical implementation was assigned to the renowned printer Stefano Paolini. In 1628, the Congregation made the decision to cast two types of Georgian fonts. An enormous amount of material about Georgia is preserved in the "Propaganda Fide" archive: missionaries write

about Georgian culture, geography, and politics; the repository houses the correspondence between the Pope of Rome and Georgian kings.

Review and Discussion: The first Georgian printed publications are: "Georgian Alphabet with Prayers," "Georgian-Italian Dictionary," the Georgian translation of the Catholic prayer "Litania Lauretana," and Francesco-Maria Maggio's "Georgian Grammar."

In 1629, the first Georgian printed book, the "Georgian-Italian Dictionary," was published in Rome. The title page of this book states that it was compiled by Stefano Paolini with the assistance of the Georgian ambassador Nicephorus Irbach (Nikoloz Cholokashvili). This book contains up to three hundred Georgian words, the Georgian alphabet, and an index of Italian words.

In the same year, a second Georgian book, "Georgian Alphabet with Prayers," was printed in Rome. Several variants of this book exist: in one, the Italian title is given alongside the Georgian title of the prayer; in the other, it is not. In the 1614 edition of this collection, the prayer "Credo in unum Deum" ("I believe in one God") is presented in 20 different languages and dialects: Latin, Italian, French, Spanish, Portuguese, German, English, Irish, Dutch, Polish, Hungarian, Lithuanian, Welsh... This edition is preserved in the National Library of Paris.

In 1643 and 1670, the missionary Francesco-Maria Maggio published the "Grammar of the Georgian Language" twice, which he dedicated to Pope Urban VIII. The first part of the work is devoted to the grammatical rules of the Georgian or Iberian language; the second part to the rules of the Turkish (Arabic) language. Maggio's grammar of the "Georgian or Iberian language" consists of four parts: Orthography, Etymology, Syntax, Prosody.

Maggio relies on the system of philological grammar and proceeds from the grammatical categories and processes of the Latin language. Despite all its short-

comings, Maggio's grammar holds a special place. Before Marie Brosset's "Georgian Grammar" came out (1834), European scholars became acquainted with the Georgian language through Francesco-Maria Maggio's grammar.

Printing books in Georgian in Europe had great significance. European missionaries became interested in Georgian culture. Additionally, the ground was being prepared for printing Georgian books in Georgia itself. The circumstance that the publication of the first Georgian printed books was carried out on an international basis deserves special attention. This fact indicates that in the 17th century, the printed word already represented a quite effective weapon for deepening international cultural relations.

A prayer to the Mother of God, "Litania Lauretana," translated from Latin into Georgian by Nicephorus Irbach (Nikoloz Cholokashvili), was also published in this religious institution's printing press. Let us try to understand what caused Nicephorus Irbach's so clearly manifested interest in "Litania Lauretana," that is, toward the Catholic prayer dedicated to the Mother of God. Or what specific circumstances facilitated his translation of this prayer into the Georgian language. Despite the fact that "Litania Lauretana" is a Catholic prayer, it belongs to that category of Christian prayers that enjoyed almost equal rights in both Catholic and Orthodox churches.

The missionaries initially went to Gori, which at this time was considered the citadel of missionary activities, then moved to western Georgia - to Samegrelo. Here, the missionaries performed the prayer to the Mother of God. A bell would ring as a sign of prayer, after which a secret prayer would be performed, and immediately the Litany of the Most Holy Mother of God would follow. Beyond doubt is the fact that "in the form of the Litany of the Most Holy Mother of God," "Litania Lauretana" is meant here, but not the Latin text of this prayer, but rather its Georgian translation published in Rome in 1629. The latter was brought to Georgia from Italy by missionaries in the 1630s along with the first Georgian printed books.

From the perspective of printing design, the external appearance of the Georgian text of "Litania Lauretana" is much more impressive than that of the "Alphabet" or the "Georgian-Italian Dictionary." Above the Georgian text of the Litany, inscribed in two lines, is a very distinctive decorated title, each component word of which is separated by three dots on the right. At the bottom of the sixtieth page of the Georgian text of the "Litany," below a drawn line, is an Italian inscription: "Printed in Rome, at the printing press of Propaganda Fide (Holy Congregation) with the permission of the highest ecclesiastical authority." The entire text - the Georgian translation of "Litania Lauretana" - is cast in an original, very beautiful ornamental frame. Its separately published Georgian text looks completely different, thanks to the impressive engraving. The engraving is the detail that crowns the prayer, which is placed above the title. The subject of the engraving is of biblical content. On it is presented with artistic refinement a composition whose central theme is the worship of the Mother of God to the newborn Christ in the presence of Saint Joseph, where the kneeling Mary humbly worships the newborn God-man, who lies on a white cloth

spread on hay. On the left is given a fragment of the stable - with livestock, which announces Christ's birth in a stable, while on the right appear relatively distant figures of men who by their clothing resemble shepherds. Above the engraving, in the central part, is depicted a choir of angels in the rays of the sun, which contributes to the perception of the image imprinted on the engraving in its entirety.

The foundation of the "Litany," as a Catholic prayer, is sought in the content of the Old Testament of the Bible. The first recognized documentary information about the prayer itself is dated to 1531, 1547, and 1554, though officially it was confirmed only in 1587 by Pope Sixtus V. The most famous litanies are considered to be the so-called "Litany of All Saints" and the Litany of the Mother of God of Loreto, or "Litania Lauretana." From 1575 onward, other "new litanies" appeared, which is why the Vatican implemented a series of measures to protect the prayer from any violation, from the introduction of any changes and corrections to it. Apparently, such strictness of Catholic censorship determined that the text of the prayer has not undergone any significant changes over the centuries. To identify and characterize the inaccuracies allowed in the text of the Georgian translation of "Litania Lauretana" performed in 1629, it seems justified to compare it, first of all, with the corresponding Georgian text, which was published much later, in 1905 in Tbilisi, and which is still used by believing Georgian Catholics today. The latter in its content basically corresponds to the 1629 Georgian text of "Litania Lauretana," with the difference that instead of the Litany of the Mother of God of Loreto, it has as its title "Litany of the All-Holy," and the number of lines is not sixty but sixty-four.

Conclusion: A review of the Georgian translation of "Litania Lauretana" allows for the unmistakable general conclusion that already in the 17th century, the printed word represented a quite effective weapon for achieving both political and religious purposes. The possibility of using the printed word of that time for this purpose is confirmed by the joint participation of representatives of Italy, Greece, France, and Georgia in the publication of the first Georgian printed texts.

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